

Shannon's Entropy, Probability Changes and Average Energy

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In a previous note (1) we considered dE (thermal) = Sum over i $e_i dP(i)$ where $P(i)$ is the probability to have e_i . In other words, one has the constant vector $\{e_i\}$ forming a dot product with the differential operator $\{dP(i)\}$. We suggested one might wish to find a vector function $\{G(P(i))\}$ and create the dot product $S = - \text{Sum over } i G(P(i)) P(i)$ such that $dS = - \text{Sum over } i G(P(i)) dP(i)$. For small changes $\{dP(i)\}$ the vector $\{G(P(i))\}$ is a constant of the system with $G = \ln$ the logarithm function as a solution.

In this note we compare this picture with that of information theory for which one writes $P_{\text{overall}} = \text{Product over } i P(i)$ [to the power $N P(i)$] where N is large. This approach also leads to the form of Shannon's entropy i.e. one does not need to find the function \ln - it appears automatically, but one needs a large N limit to formulate the problem whereas no such assumption is needed in (1). We consider the situation of $P(i) \rightarrow P(i) + dP(i)$. We ultimately try to link dE thermal to the change in the product probability of $P(i)$'s in a gas with dS being linked to the change in the product probability which itself is linked to the overall number of arrangements.

We also consider how the form \ln is associated with converting $P(i)P(j)$ into a sum i.e. $\ln(P(i)) + \ln(P(j))$. For example, for an ideal gas one may consider two body elastic collisions. Assuming that $P(i)P(j) = P(k)P(l)$ and given $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$ one may take the \ln of the former and associate $\ln(P(i))$ with $-e_i/T$, where T is a constant. Thus one uses the idea of \ln converting a product to a sum and the idea of conservation which in this particular case is conservation of energy. One may ask how this links with the picture of $P(i)\ln(P(i))$ leading to a locally constant vector? We argue that one may consider two particles and consider a change in $P(i)$ i.e. $P(i) + dP(i)$. In such a case it is not $\ln(P(i)) + \ln(P(i))$ which is linked with conservation, but one is interested in the conservation rule $P(i) + P(j) = \text{constant}$. We show that it is form $P(i)\ln(P(i))$ which is then linked with a conservation law namely $\text{Sum over } i dP(i) = 0$ where $i = 1, 2$ in this case. Thus there is a link between the derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution strictly from $P(i)P(j)$ and $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$ and Shannon's entropy which is related to $\ln(P(i))$, but is slightly different, namely $P(i)\ln(P(i))$, in order to make use of conservation of probability.

Shannon's Entropy and a Constant Vector Function of Probability

In (1) we argued that one may obtain Shannon's entropy by creating a dot product:

$$S = - \{ G(P(i)) \} \text{ dot } \{ P(i) \} = - \text{Sum over } i G(P(i)) P(i) \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{such that } dS = \{ G(P(i)) \} \text{ dot } \{ dP(i) \} \quad ((2))$$

The motivation for this is that for average energy given by: $E_{\text{ave}} = \text{Sum over } i e_i P(i)$:

$$d E_{\text{ave}} (\text{thermal}) = \text{Sum over } i e_i dP(i) \quad ((3))$$

For ((3)) one has a constant vector $\{e_i\}$ and so at worst one would like to have a $\{G(P(i))\}$ which does not change when $P(i) \rightarrow P(i) + dP(i)$ (to mimic ((3))). At best, $\{G(P(i))\}$ might be directly linked to the constant vector $\{-e_i/T\}$ if one equates ((3)) and ((2)) although this is a special case.

We found in ((1)) that $G(P(i)) = \ln(P(i))$ satisfies this requirement leading to:

$$S = - \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i)) \quad ((4))$$

No idea of large N or arrangements is needed to obtain ((4)) and one has:

$$dS = - \sum_i \ln(P(i)) dP(i) \quad ((5))$$

Two key points are needed in obtaining ((5)):

A: One needs a function such that $P(i) dG/dP(i) = dP(i)$ and not $F(P(i)) dP(i)$ ((7))

B One needs conservation in particular: $\sum_i dP(i) = 0$ ((8))

Product Probabilities in an Information Theory Treatment of Shannon's Entropy

In the above section, a dot product type function $S = - \sum_i G(P(i)) P(i)$ was created which has certain properties namely $dS = - \sum_i G(P(i)) dP(i)$. In this section we consider N outcomes of P(i) results where N is large. The number of i outcomes is approximately $NP(i)$ and the overall product probability is:

$$P_{\text{overall}} = \text{Product over } i \ P(i)^{NP(i)} \quad ((9))$$

$P_{\text{overall}} = 1 / \text{number of arrangements}$

The $\ln\{\text{number of arrangements}\}$ may be calculated by using factorials and then using Stirling's approximation because N is large.

We ask: What is the effect on ((9)) if $P(i) \rightarrow P(i) + dP(i)$?

$$P_{\text{overall}} = P_{\text{overall initial}} * \text{Product over } i \ P(i)^{N dP(i)} \quad ((10))$$

At this point, no $\ln(P(i))$ appears. One may notice the presence of P(i) in ((10)) and not $P(i)[1+dP(i)/P(i)]$. This is due to two points. First: $[1+dP(i)/P(i)] = \exp\{\ln(1+dP(i)/P(i))\}$ and secondly $\ln(1+dP(i)/P(i)) \approx dP(i)/P(i)$. This combines with $NP(i)$ in the exponent to yield:

$$\sum_i dP(i) = 0 \quad ((11))$$

Thus there is a conservation law at work and the factor $1+dP(i)/P(i)$ has no effect overall. As a result, if one takes the \ln of P overall one has:

$$\ln(P_{\text{overall}}) = \ln(P_{\text{overall initial}}) + \sum \text{over } i \ N \ dP(i) \ \ln(P(i)) \quad ((11))$$

This is of a very similar form as:

$$E_{\text{ave}} = E_{\text{ave initial}} + \sum \text{over } i \ e_i \ dP(i) \quad ((12))$$

((10)) may describe probabilities over a long period of time. Over such a period there emerges a pattern in the overall time sequence of probabilities i.e. $NP(i)$ instances of event i . One may note that $NP(i)+NdP(i)$ remaining in the exponent of ((10)) indicates this is the new expected number of i outcomes. As a result, a probabilistic sequence over a long time mimics an average energy scenario. This may also represent a sequence over a long period of time if there is a single quantum particle represented by ((12)) where e_i are the bound state energy levels. In such a case, one may link ((11)) and ((12)) by:

$$P(i) = \exp(-e_i/T) / C(T) \quad ((13))$$

This leads to $E-TS = -T \ln(C(T))$ (= Helmholtz free energy ((14))

Defining Information Without a Large N Approximation

In (3) a derivation of information is given which does not make use of arrangements or large N scenarios. There it is argued that $\text{Information}(pq) = \text{Information}(p) + \text{Information}(q)$ where p and q are probabilities. $-\ln$ is immediately a possible solution. The average of information is then yields Shannon's entropy.

Two Particle Scattering

It may be noted that in ((10)) one may have $dP_1 = -dP_2$ and $dP(i)=0$ for $i>2$. In such a case only two probabilities change yet $\sum \text{over } i \ dP(i) = 0$. It may be further noted that the form $\exp(-e_i/T)$ in ((13)) may be obtained without any notion of sequences i.e. one may consider two body elastic scattering with time reversal balance:

$$E_i+E_j = E_k + E_l \quad \text{and} \quad P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_k)P(e_l) = \text{constant} \quad ((15))$$

Taking \ln of ((15)) to convert a product into a sum and linking to e_i 's yields $\ln(P(e_i)$ unnormalized) = $-e_i/T$ where T is a constant. Thus \ln is used to convert products to sums and there is conservation, but of energy at the \ln level. At this point, one has $\ln(P(e_i))$ as a quantity, but not $P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$. In other words, one has an equilibrium scenario with additive $\ln(P(e_i))$ pieces such that when $\ln(P(e_i))+\ln(P(e_j)) = \text{constant} = \text{function}(e_i+e_j, T)$, any other $\ln(P(e_k)) + \ln(P(e_l)) = \text{constant}$ has the same probability.

How does $P(e_i)\ln(P(e_i))$ appear? A simple way is to consider $E_{ave} = \sum_i e_i P(e_i)$. Then $E_{ave} = \sum_i \{-T\ln(P(e_i)) + T\ln(C(T))\} P(e_i)$ or $E_{ave} = TS + T\ln(C(T))$. Another way is to consider:

$P(i) \rightarrow P(i) + dP(i)$? (In such a case, the constant T might change which means that e_i values do not change.) Then:

$$P(e_i)[1+dP(e_i)/P(e_i)] P(e_j) [1+ dP(e_j)/P(e_j)] = \text{constant}^2 \quad ((16))$$

One might consider a gas with only $P(e_i)$ and $P(e_j)$ changing. In such a case $dP(e_i) = -dP(e_j)$ by conservation of probability. In order to make use of this conservation, one needs to consider some issues.

$P(e_i)$ is the probability of having one e_i particle at some point. $P(e_i)^{N P(e_i)}$ is the product probability of all e_i 's in the gas. Thus one changes from a sequence in time to a many particle picture where at an instant in time one has $N P(i)$ i states if N is large. The product probability for $P(e_i)$'s and $P(e_j)$'s is:

$$\{P(e_i)[1+dP(e_i)/P(e_i)]\}^{N(P(e_i)+dP(e_i))} \{P(e_j) [1+ dP(e_j)/P(e_j)]\}^{N(P(e_j)+dP(e_j))} \quad ((17))$$

Writing $1+dP/P = \exp(\ln(1+dP/P)) = \exp(dP/P)$ and making use of conservation of probability shows that ((17)) is equivalent to:

$$\text{Exp}\{ N(P(e_i)+dP(e_i)) \ln(P(e_i)) + N(P(e_j)+dP(e_j)) \ln(P(e_j)) \} \quad ((18))$$

Thus even for a two particle scenario, one has the notion of:

$$S = -\sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i)) \text{ such that } dS = -\sum_i \ln(P(e_i)) dP(e_i) \quad ((19))$$

((19)) also holds if one changes all $P(i)$ such that $\sum_i dP(i) = 0$. In general, one would want to have all $P(e_i)$ change if one uses $P(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)/C(T)$ and the change is due to a change in T the temperature.

((18)) is equivalent to $\exp(-S)$.

If one changes T slightly, one changes $P(e_i)$ values and S as well.

We note that $dE_{thermal} = \sum_i e_i dP(e_i) = TdS$ where

$$dS = -\sum_i \ln(P(e_i)) dP(e_i) .$$

NdS is the change in the \ln of the product probability of a gas as $P(e_i) \rightarrow P(e_i)+dP(e_i)$. Thus there is a microscopic probabilistic interpretation of this dS change which when multiplied by the parameter T yields the change in thermal energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that as in (1), one may find a function strictly of probabilities of the form: $S = -\sum_i P(i) G(P(i))$ such that $dS = -\sum_i G(P(i)) dP(i)$. $\ln(P(i)) = G(P(i))$ is a solution obtained without need of arrangements or large N . It is, however, interesting to consider a large N sequence (perhaps over time) of i events. An alternative is to consider a many body ideal gas with $N P(i)$ particles in state i . This may also apply to a single quantum bound particle which has energy levels of e_i .

From information theory it is known that $\ln(\text{overall product probability}) = \exp \{ \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i)) \}$. We consider changing $P(i) \rightarrow P(i) + dP(i) = P(i) (1 + dP(i)/P(i))$. In the exponent one has $N(P(i) + dP(i))$. Taking \ln of the base and using conservation of probability i.e. $\sum_i dP(i) = 0$ leads to a result of $\exp(-S - dS)$ where $dS = -\sum_i \ln(P(i)) dP(i)$. Thus $\ln(P(i))$ has the form of a constant vector for small $dP(i)$ changes. dS , however, shows how the \ln of the product probability changes. One may show that $dE_{\text{thermal}} = \sum_i e_i dP(i) = T dS$, so one has a statistical picture of a change in thermal energy as equivalent to a change in the \ln of the product probabilities of a gas multiplied by a constant parameter T (using Shannon's entropy).

References

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